

A Study on Work-Life Balances among Working Mothers at Schools in Madurai

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Abstract

The purpose of the study is to investigate and identify the work-life balance among the Working Mothers at schools and the socio- economic condition of the respondents. The quantitative research design was used in this study. Fifty Respondents were selected from the universe as a sample size. The interview was targeted for female working mothers at schools in Madurai district. The main discussion of the paper is how married women working in schools manage to have a better work-life balance and stress free life.

Keywords: Work-life balance, Employer, Employee, Stress, Technology

Introduction

Work-life Balance is balancing the two sides of life - family life and work life. In the work-life balance is very challenge to dealing or balancing the professional life and personal life.

It is a comfortable state of equilibrium achieved between an Employee's primary priorities of their employment position and their private lifestyle. Most Psychologists would agree that the demands of an Employee's career should not overwhelm the individual's ability to enjoy a satisfying personal life outside of the business environment

The ideal work-life balance is open for discussion. Freethinker and Paul Krassner said that Anthropologists often define happiness as having little or no differentiation between an individual's professional and personal lives. Work-life balance is a typical issue due to the increased amount of technology that removes the importance of physical location in defining the work-life balance. Previously it was difficult or impossible to take work home and so there was a clear line between the professional and individual.

The increase in mobile technology, cloud-based software and the proliferation of the Internet has made it much easier for Employees to be 'permanently' at work, blurring the distinction between the Professional and individual. Some commentators argue that smart phones and 'always-on' access to the workplace have replaced the

authoritarian control of Managers. Stress is a common feature of a poor work-life balance. In the information economy mental stress has been identified as a significant economic and health problem, causing by a perceived need of Employees to do more in less time.

A key issue in the work-life balance debate is where responsibility lies for ensuring Employees to have a good work-life balance. The general feeling is that Employers have a responsibility to the health of their Employees; apart from the moral responsibility, stressed-out Employees are less productive and more likely to make errors.

Importance of Work-Life Balance

Working on a job for a company and making a career can be an extremely time consuming duty for any Employee. Employees are busy at their offices throughout the day and sometimes, during weekends. That gives them very a little time to interact with their family members. Because of high pressure of work, often family members get neglected. Also, stressful jobs cause the health of Employees to deteriorate. This is where Work-life balance come into the picture. Work-life balance concept allows an Employee to maintain a fine balance in the time he or she gives to work as well as to personal matters. By having a good balance, people can have a quality of work life. This helps to increase productivity at workplace as the Employee is relaxed about his personal commitments. It also allows the Employee to give quality time with family to spend vacations, leisure time, work on his/her health etc. Hence Work-life balance is extremely important for employees and increases their motivation to work for the company.

Companies are increasingly recognizing the importance of helping their employees achieve this balance as more staff are experiencing conflict between their work and personal roles. In today's age, many workers are seeing their personal responsibilities increased, from childcare and elderly care, to volunteer work, and family commitments. This comes at a time when their work responsibilities are also increasing, resulting in a conflict between personal and work commitments and an increase in stress.

Another factor which is contributing greatly to the difficulty in achieving a Work-life balance is the changing landscape in how and where employees are expected to work. As more and more companies embrace the technological age and move into globalization, work is no longer restricted to the workplace. Employees can work from almost any location with the use of Laptops, Tablets, and Smart Phones; and telecommuting is on the increase. Employees can access work Emails and assignments 24/7, meaning that they can also be accessible to Employers and clients. Although there are multiple benefits to this flexible working pattern, it can run the risk of blurring the lines between work and personal life. Remote working also means that staff may now find that their typical work week is no longer restricted to the traditional 40 hours a week.

The result of a poor balance between work and personal life not only affects Employees, but it also affects the companies that they work for. The stress of Employee can increase to the level of burnout, resulting in lower productivity at work, a higher potential for stress related health problems and absenteeism, with the associated costs related to these being passed on to the company. In addition to this, Employees may also experience poor personal and co-worker relationships and reduced job satisfaction.

There are several ways in which companies can help encourage a Work-life balance for their Employees, both in the policies that they implement and in ensuring that managers actively encourage Employees to take advantage of these policies. Offering Employees flexible working options helps Employees design their work pattern to fit their personal commitments, ultimately reducing conflict between work and personal responsibilities. Flexible working options include allowing Employees to work from home, adjust their working hours to meet personal commitments, use remote working, compressed work weeks, and job sharing. Managers should encourages staff

to use annual leave and help Employees to set boundaries by encouraging staff not respond to work related Emails and calls during non-working hours. Some organizations are also implementing wellness programs, which include offering stress reduction and time management workshops, while others are creating wellness centers on the work site, helping to connect Employees with Physicians, mental health counselors, or on-site gyms.

An Employee's satisfaction in their personal life and their ability to meet personal commitments greatly affects their success as a worker, which greatly benefits any company. Helping Employees to achieve a good Work-life balance increases work satisfaction, increases their loyalty to their Employer, and helps Employers to achieve career longevity. A company which recognizes these benefits and implements policies to promote a Work-life balance is one which will not only see an increase in the productivity of their workforce but which also sees increased retention of staff and reduction in costs associated with high turnover.

Work-Life Balances of Working Mother's

Basically work-life balance is a challenge to both male and female. In our Indian context female work-life balance is hill upping problem. The women could play the vital role and tremendous talent of managing the both the spheres of life. If the women should be a working mother balancing work-life is mirage. In India childcare is the main responsibility of the mother and mother should be smart and a multitasked person in the family. In the same time, professional realm except their Employees to be effective and efficient in their works. Globalization causes more competition every organization. So the organization is expecting the multitasked and smart worker as a Employee.

Now a days women should have professional career for the financial development of her family. Women could have a better work-life balance when she is getting the support and help from her the family members. Working mothers have more responsibilities like childcare, personal and professional life. In such a context this present study is the need of the hour.

Research Methodology

Objectives: 1. To study socio- economic conditions of the respondents in the study area.2.To measure the work-life balance among the Working Mothers at schools.

Research Design:The Quantitative research methodology is adopted for this study. In the proposed study descriptive research design will be used.

Tool for Data Collection: A questionnaire is used for collecting data from the primary sources. A questionnaire is prepared by the researcher for collecting the data from the respondents using five point scales.

Sample – Techniques & Size: For the present study researcher used simple random sampling methods to collect data from Working Mothers in the schools. Fifty Respondents were selected from the universe as a sample size.

Data Analysis

Table 1 Distribution of Respondents Based on the No of Kids

S.No.	No of Kids	Frequency	Percentage
1	1	27	54.0
2	2	23	46.0
	Total	50	100.0

From the above table it is clear that more than half of the respondents (54%) have got one kid and remaining of the respondents (46%) has two kids

Table 2 Distribution of Respondents Based on the Age

S.No.	Age	Frequency	Percentage
1	26 to 35	22	44.0
2	36 to 45	21	42.0
3	46 to 58	7	14.0
	Total	50	100.0

Above table shows that 44% of the respondents are in the age group of 26 to 35 years, 42% of the respondents are between 36 to 45 years and only 14% are between 46 to 58 years.

Table 3 Distribution of Respondents Based on the Salary

S.No.	Salary	Frequency	Percentage
1	2700 to 5500	18	36.0
2	5600 to 8500	22	44.0
3	8600 to 15000	10	20.0
	Total	50	100.0

The table shows that 44% of the respondents are getting Rs 2700 to 5500 as salary and 36% of the respondents are getting Rs 5600 to 8500 as salary and only 20% of the respondents are getting Rs 8600 to 15000 as salary.

Table 4 Distribution of Respondents Based on the Experience

S.No.	Experience	Frequency	Percentage
1	1 to 8	24	48.0
2	9 to 17	16	32.0
3	18 to 27	10	20.0
	Total	50	100.0

The inference from the above table is half of the respondents (48%) have 1 to 8 years of experience and 32% have 9 to 17 years of experience and only 20% of the respondents have 18 to 27 year of experience.

Table 5 Distribution of Respondents Based on the Awareness on Work-Life Balance

S.No.	Awareness on Work-life balance	Frequency	Percentage
1	Yes	13	26.0
2	No	37	74.0
	Total	50	100.0

The above table it is clearly shows that Three fourth of the respondents (74%) have no awareness on work-life balance and only one fourth of the respondents (26%) have awareness on work-life balance.

Table 6 Distribution of Respondents based on the Level of Work-Life Balances

S.No.	Level of Work-life Balances	Frequency	Percentage
1	Low [51 to 88]	23	46.0
2	High [89 to 120]	27	54.0
	Total	50	100.0

It is clear that more than half of the respondents (54%) have high level of work-life balance and only 46 % of the respondent have low level of work-life balance.

Findings

- Nearly one third of the respondents (34%) have kids of 6-10 of age, one third of the respondents (34%) have kids of 11-15years, one fourth are between the age group of (20%) 16-20years and below one fourth of the respondents (12%) have kids of 1-5years.
- It is clear that more than half of the respondents (54%) have got one kid and remaining of the respondents (46%) has two kids.
- 44% of the respondents are in the age group of 26 to 35years, 42% of the respondents are between 36 to 45years and only 14% are between 46 to 58years
- 44% of the respondents are getting Rs 2700 to 5500 as salary and 36% of the respondents are getting Rs 5600 to 8500 as salary and only 20% of the respondents are getting Rs 8600 to 15000 as salary.
- Nearly half of the respondents (48%) have 1 to 8 years of experience and 32% have 9 to 17 years of experience and only 20% of the respondents have 18 to 27 year of experience.
- Three fourth of the respondents (74%) have no awareness on work-life balance and only one fourth of the respondents (26%) have awareness on work-life balance.
- More than half of the respondents (54%) have high level of work-life balance and only 46 % of the respondent have low level of work-life balance.
- There is no significant relationship between the Salary and the Work-life balance
- There is no significant difference between the No of kids and the Work-life balance.
- There is a significant difference between the respondent's awareness on work-life balance and Work-life balance.
- There is a significant difference between Age of the kids and Work-life balance.
- There is a no significant difference between salary of the respondents and Work-life
- There is a significant difference between experience of the respondents and Work-life balance.

Conclusion

“Women constitute an important section of the academic workforce. However, the present situation of a large number of well-qualified women who due to various circumstances have been left out of their jobs needs to be addressed. The problems faced are several but significantly, most often the “break in their careers” arises out of motherhood and family responsibilities.”

Achieving a good balance between work and family commitments is a growing concern for contemporary employees and organizations. There is now mounting evidence-linking work-life imbalance to reduced health and wellbeing among individuals and families. It is not surprising then that there is increasing interest among organizational stakeholders for introducing work-life balance policies in their organizations.

Work-life balance policies are most likely to be successfully mainstreamed in organizations which have a clear understanding of their business rationale and which respect the importance of work-life balance for all employees. Whatever the chosen course, it is hoped that this research project report will form a stepping stone in the process and provide a basis for reflection and debate on work-life balance issues at school (Academic sector) in Madurai.

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